

Manual for CETAF Marketplace Executive Editors

Taxonomic Expertise and Services Marketplace pilot

**A hive for finding and supplying
taxonomic expertise and services**

Introduction

This is a short manual for CETAF personnel who manage the taxonomic e-services content of the CETAF Marketplace (executive editors). Users can suggest new services through a form, which are stored in the Marketplace backend (Cordra). These need to be reviewed and made public by an executive editor in the Cordra backend. The editor also needs to add a quality score for the service.

Finding new service suggestions

1. Go to <https://marketplace.cetaf.org/cordra>.
2. Sign in with your username (admin) and password.
3. Select Show Only ->TaxonomicService.
4. Select the arrows left from the search bar to show advanced search options.

The screenshot shows the 'Sample Document Repository' interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links: Get Started, About, API Docs, All Objects, Show Only (dropdown), Types (dropdown), Admin (dropdown), and a user profile 'admin' with a 'Sign Out' link. Below the navigation bar, there is a search area with a 'Show/Hide Advanced Search Options' dropdown. The search bar contains the text 'type:"TaxonomicService"'. To the right of the search bar are 'Search' and 'Create' buttons. Below the search bar, there are 'Sort By' dropdowns set to 'Created On' and 'Ascending', and a 'Facet On' input field with the text 'ex: /name'. A 'JSON' link is visible on the right. The main content area displays a service suggestion for 'Discover Life' with a detailed description and metadata: 'Modified: 2025-01-17T10:57:11.541Z' and 'Created: 2025-01-14T13:00:34.333Z'.

5. Select Sort By: Created On to see the latest new service suggestions.

Managing a service suggestion

1. Select a service from the list by clicking its name.
2. **Click edit** so you can edit the content.
3. Review the content and make changes where necessary. Note that you can use markdown in the Description field.
4. Accept or reject the suggested service by changing the Status in the service description record to Accepted or Rejected. The service becomes publicly visible when the status is: Accepted. Do not delete the service description except if the record was just made for testing purposes. Accept only services that are in scope of the marketplace and that are of sufficient quality to be included (no beta or pilot services).

Date Modified *
2025-01-17T10:57:11.540Z
Date the service was published, f
Status *
accepted
proposed
accepted
rejected

5. Change the Rating Value to give an indication about the quality of the service (displayed as a quality indicator bar in the marketplace). The value is a percentage: 100 means the service is excellent.
6. Make a comment about the rating value given in the Rating Explanation to explain your score. This comment is not visible in the front-end. Note however that the Cordra back-end is publicly accessible for people who know the URL and through the API.

Rating Value *
80
The rating for the content on a scale from 0 to 100
Rating Explanation
some key information is missing like data licenses and the site is a bit hard to navigate.
A short explanation (e.g. one to two sentences) providing background context and other info

7. **Save your changes.**

the end.